

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-6-103-OJH-2% 40 03 RAC	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	20231026
Vial:	31	Acq. Method Set:	2%210400 40 03
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	6 1030
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	45.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	10/26/2023 8:02:29 PM CST		
Date Processed:	10/26/2023 9:56:31 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	20.063	1586216	29.45	48737
2	23.871	1097684	20.38	28564
3	29.141	1092887	20.29	23459
4	30.687	1609522	29.88	29918

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-6-101-OJH-2% 40 03 ASY	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	20231026
Vial:	32	Acq. Method Set:	2%210400 40 03
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	6 101
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	45.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	10/26/2023 8:48:10 PM CST		
Date Processed:	10/26/2023 9:59:34 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	19.482	12808933	93.18	388280
2	23.197	536415	3.90	13523
3	28.122	373652	2.72	8164
4	30.430	27739	0.20	-611